

CONDITION MONITORING OF MOTORCYCLE SUSPENSION USING VIBRATION ANALYSIS

A PROJECT REPORT

SUBMITTED BY

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BONAFIDE CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “Condition Monitoring of Motorcycle Suspension using Vibration Analysis” submitted by **Achyuthan U.K. , Atindra Krishnan, Eshwar .G , R. Karthik** for the award of the **Degree of Bachelor of Technology in Mechanical Engineering** is a bonafide record of the work carried out under my/our guidance and supervision at Amrita School of Engineering, Coimbatore.

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DECLARATION

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ABSTRACT

Healthy, trouble-free suspension system in a motorcycle is vital for proper handling and braking of the vehicle, besides safety and comfort of passengers. Early detection of incipient faults in the suspension system will prevent catastrophic failures that will endanger the rider. Prognostic methods based on vibration signature analysis and classification algorithms have been successfully implemented in several large stationary equipment. Our project aims to identify, based on vibration analysis, the machine learning algorithm that most accurately classifies two common faults in motorcycle suspensions, namely, change in fork oil viscosity, and leakage of fork oil due to wear, at two different vehicle speeds. Vibration signals were obtained for suspensions having the aforementioned defects, and, for a suspension in good condition as well. These signals were then analysed using different families of classifier algorithms through Weka, an open source machine learning software developed by University of Waikato, New Zealand. It was established that for a vehicle speed of 15 kilometres per hour, the C4.5 algorithm exhibited the highest efficiency of 96.3185 percent, whereas for a speed of 30 kilometres per hour, the K-star algorithm had the highest efficiency of 87.037 percent.

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INTRODUCTION

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1. Motorcycle Suspension

Motorcycle suspension, in its simplest form, is for rider comfort, rider safety, and proper handling. The main objective is keeping the rubber tires fixed to the road. A proper suspension must be able to absorb the shocks resulting from imperfections on the road, while increasing cornering, braking, and acceleration thresholds. Suspension is the component that allows the movement of tires over the obstacles, thus stopping the discomfort to the rider, and also effectively dissipates the resulting kinetic energy. Through years of development, with manufacturers finding multiple ways to achieve this task, it has now currently evolved to telescopic forks in the front, and a swing-arm for the rear due to its simplicity and low cost.

Front wheel is the steering control for the vehicle, and thus a pair of telescopic forks is used in front for better handling and safety. A fork is basically a large shock absorber consisting of an internal spring and a hydraulic damper. A typical fork has a fork tube at the top, a triple clamp to hold it with the vehicle, and a piston at the bottom. In modern sport bikes, and in every off-road bikes, this system is inverted, known as the inverted telescopic fork. A typical telescopic fork is shown in figure 1. In the rear suspension, swing arm is primarily used, which pivots one end to the vehicle, and the other end is attached to the rear wheel for swing action by maintaining the suspension axis perpendicular to the other end. There may be one or two shock absorbers, depending on the manufacturer. This project focuses on the front suspension as it has greater impact on handling and safety. Nevertheless, this project can be extended to rear suspension as well.

Fig. 1 A typical Suspension fork.

A failure in the suspension system can significantly affect vehicle handling and rider comfort, especially at lower speeds. Some of the commonly occurring faults are:

1. Bent fork tube, which occurs mainly due to accident.
2. Change in viscosity of damper oil due to wear and tear as it becomes old.
3. Leakage of damper oil due to damage in the fork sealant.
4. Corroded inner walls of the fork tube, which again results in oil leak.

Though there may be other faults occurring in a suspension system, the aforementioned faults are the frequently occurring ones. A bent fork can be easily detected through visual detection, whereas the other faults are hard to detect, and there is no direct method for this. Also, motorcycle suspension systems are often not properly maintained. Thus condition monitoring of suspension system is essential as it helps to maintain proper functioning of suspension, and fast detection of the type of faults that occur. This will also help to reduce the time and cost involved in the maintenance of suspension systems.

This project focuses on two of the above mentioned problems:

1. Leak of damper oil.
2. Change in viscosity of oil due to wear and tear.

Since bent tubes can be easily detected with naked eye, and corroded inner walls of the fork has the same effect as that of leaking fork, these two faults have not been considered for analysis.

1.2 Viscosity

Two faulty conditions were dealt with, which were compared with a good suspension. Old and worn out oil needs a quantifiable parameter to distinguish it from good oil. Thus, viscosity is the parameter that is mainly affected as the oil is worn out, and it is also a critical parameter in the performance of a shock absorber.

Viscosity is the measure of resistance of a fluid to withstand shear stress or in other words, it is the resistance to flow. It is the most critical parameter as it can affect the wear rate. The viscosity of a fluid is dependent on its temperature. Viscosity is inversely proportional to temperature. As the temperature increases, the viscosity of the oil decreases and vice-versa.

It is generally represented in two common forms:

- **Dynamic Viscosity (μ):** It is the internal resistance offered by the fluid to flow. This is generally interpreted as friction equivalent of solids in fluids. It is measured in milli Pascal Second (mPa.s) or centi poise (cP).
- **Kinematic Viscosity (ν):** It is the resistance offered by the fluid to undergo shear strain under the force of gravity. It is generally measured in mm²/sec or cSt (centi stoke). It is dynamic viscosity (μ) divided by the density of the fluid.

For this project, only kinematic viscosities were considered since oil viscosities are generally specified as kinematic viscosities.

1.3 Condition Monitoring

Condition Monitoring is a strategy for maintenance which aims at observing the health of a machine, and detects its failure by keenly observing any one critical parameter of the machine such as noise, vibration, temperature, image, pressure, current, and voltage. Condition monitoring helps in quicker detection of faults by analyzing the trends in the data of the critical parameter for different conditions of the machine. Unlike in planned maintenance, condition monitoring waits for some indication of failure before the maintenance action is taken. Thus, condition monitoring helps in faster but also less expensive maintenance of a machine.

Advantages of condition monitoring

Condition Monitoring has many advantages:

- It does not disrupt the working of a machine. It can be performed even when the machine is running.
- The cost due to failure of asset, and thus the overall cost is minimized.
- Reliability of the equipment is improved.
- Unexpected downtime due to catastrophic failure is reduced to a great extent.
- The overall time spent on maintenance is reduced.
- Overtime, and thus the cost associated with it are reduced by proper scheduling of activities.
- Emergency situations are avoided, and thus the requirement of spare parts during an emergency is lowered.

- Enhanced worker safety.
- Possibility of collateral damage to the system are reduced.

Disadvantages of condition monitoring

In spite of being the most optimum form of maintenance, condition monitoring has its own associated disadvantages:

- It is expensive due to high end test equipment, and also due to the cost involved in analyzing the database.
- Skilled and trained professionals are required, which again adds to the expenses.
- Working condition may disrupt the performance of the sensors, and thus the overall effectiveness of condition monitoring.
- Maintenance periods are unpredictable.
- Requires change in mindset of the entire organization, and change in assets, in order to have efficient practice of condition monitoring.

1.4 Algorithms Used

1.4.1 Decision Tree Algorithms

Decision Tree Algorithm pictorially depicts the classification of vibration signals obtained, in the form of a tree. Each leaf represents different conditions of the suspension, and the branching that leads to the leaves are based on statistical features, their impact, and their associated probabilities for each condition. A decision tree follows a flowchart like structure. Here, each node is a trial of a trait, and each branch of the flow chart shows the result of each trial, and at the end each nodule is the decision taken after computing all traits. It provides a detailed descriptive analysis for the various probabilities. The decision tree follows the classic *if else* syntax where if *condition 1* is satisfied then *result 1*, and if not satisfied then *result 2*. Machine learning uses decision tree as a means of predictive model to determine the conclusion from the various trials of the attribute. Data comes in the form of

$$(x, Y) = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_k, Y) \quad (1)$$

Where Y is the target variable whose output we try to predict using the input vector x consisting of the data records $(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_k)$.

The Decision Tree algorithms used here are C4.5 and Naïve Bayes algorithms.

C4.5: Developed by Quinlan (1996), C4.5 is an extension of an older algorithm ID3, which was also developed by Quinlan. The decisions made by C4.5 can be used for classification, and it is for this reason that the algorithm can be used as a statistical classifier. It uses information entropy to formulate decisions. In Information theory, Information entropy can be defined as the expected value or the average of each piece of information. The probability distribution of the input data, and the information of each event, add up to give an expected average value of the target variable. This is done by choosing the feature of the data that most effectively splits the set of obtained signals into one category or the other. J48 is the method of implementation of C4.5 algorithm in WEKA 3.6.

NB tree: The Naive Bayes classifier is a probabilistic classifier that uses Bayes' theorem to arrive at the decisions in the decision tree. The Bayes' theorem works on the principle that the probability of one event is based on the conditions that affect this event, and hence this event is not independent of the probability of the characteristic conditions. The input data can be described as $X=(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k)$. Let the condition be represented as C_k . The probability of X given C_k is now represented as

$$P(C_k|X) = P(C_k)*P(X|C_k)/P(X) \quad (2)$$

Naïve Bayes' algorithm calculates an estimate for the class probability from the training set or by using priors of the class itself. To create the criteria for the distribution of the classes, nonparametric modules are created from the training set. Since it employs Naïve Bayes' theorem as the decision criteria for the decision tree, this algorithm differs from the C 4.5 algorithm in its application.

1.4.2 Instance Based Algorithms

In machine learning, instance-based learning (sometimes called memory-based learning) is a family of learning algorithms that, instead of performing explicit generalization, compares new problem instances with instances seen in training, which have been stored in memory. This type of learning is a type of lazy learning where it constructs premises from the training instances.

- **IB1 algorithm:** Uses normalized Euclidean distance to find the test instance closest to the training instances, and predicts the same class as this training instance. In case of repetition in instances for the same training class, the instance identified first is considered to be ideal and satisfactory.
- **K* algorithm:** K* is an instance-based classifier, which uses a similarity function to compare the class of training instances with the class of input test instances. It uses information entropy function, unlike other instance based classifiers that use Euclidean distance to measure the similarity.

1.4.3 Functions based algorithms

- **Logistic Regression:**

In logistic regression, the algorithm provides us with the chance that an input variable will belong to any one of the classes that are available.

Logistic regression is used to predict categorical variables, that is, the variables that have binary categories (yes/no) or multiple categories. (here- good suspension, old oil, and oil leakage).

- **Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO):**

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a type of classifier algorithm that works on the basis of separation of values by constructing a line or hyper plane in multi-dimensional workspace in order to categorize the data obtained. These hyper-planes are known as decision planes and they define decision boundaries. SVM can be performed in four different types and each has its own working and efficiency.

These are:

1. Classification SVM –type 1
2. Classification SVM-type 2
3. Regression SVM-type 1
4. Regression SVM –type 2

SMO is an implementation of SVM, and can perform all the above mentioned four types. It is a better implementation of SVM compared to most of the other available solvers. In order to train a support vector machine, a very large quadratic programming (QP) optimization problem has to be solved. SMO solves the small QP analytically, and thus avoids the need to perform laborious numerical QP optimizations in an inner loop.

SMO requires a linear training set size, and thus the SMO can handle very large training sets. In the absence of matrix computation, SMO scales from the linear to quadratic set size rather than the linear to cubic set size that the conventional SVM algorithm scales to. As a result, these SMOs can handle real world data sets, which are very sparse, about 1000 times faster than the conventional algorithms.

1.5 Conclusion

It can therefore be seen that suspension is one of the crucial components in a motorcycle, and thus requires serious attention in order to ensure a better and safer ride. As already discussed, condition monitoring, a form of predictive maintenance, is the best tool available in terms of cost, time, and efficiency of maintenance, and this project focuses on the Condition Monitoring of Motorcycle Front Suspension.

LITERATURE SURVEY

2.0 LITERATURE SURVEY

- According to (Quinlan, 1996), C4.5 is a system that learns decision tree modifiers. The paper addressed the concerns of C 4.5 not taking full advantage of possible local discretization. However with addition of modifications, the algorithm's use of continuous attributes was able to be improved. The results were compared with a thorough global discretization scheme, and the algorithm's improved results were displayed. The paper suggested the addition of non-binary splits to make the decision trees more intelligible and more accurate. The paper helped to understand the overall functioning of the C 4.5 algorithm, and how it can be implemented in the project. It was ideal due to its binary decision tree split and high efficiency in handling large and continuous data with large local discretization.
- (Sun et al., 2007) noted that fault diagnosis is highly employing the use of data mining for its purposes. Here, principal component analysis (PCA) was used to reduce the number of characteristics of features, and then the C-4.5 program was trained to formulate the required decision tree. A solution that is most optimal was generated when compared to the solution obtained in the absence of PCA. A rotating machine was used in 6 running states: normal or without any defect, unbalance, rotor radial rub, oil whirl, shaft crack, and a simultaneous state of unbalance and radial rub. A Bently Rotor Kit RK4 was used to test and validate the methodology. This experiment forms the basis of the project where analogous to the fault simulation in the rotating machine similar faults were replicated on the motorcycle suspension. (Good, leaking oil sealant, and old oil)
- (Yan and Gao, 2007) elaborated on the approximate entropy that enumerates the frequency of a time series like a vibration signal that might come from a rotating object or in our case the motorcycle suspension. As the machine undergoes wear and tear the regularity of the vibration signal suffers as the motion become irregular, and this results in the approximate entropy of the body increasing. A side-by-side comparison of the degradation of the regularity of the vibration signals with the

increase in the approximate entropy value was presented in the paper. Vibration signals were extracted on a bearing test bed. The paper mentioned that the value of approximate entropy can help predict the condition of the working product. This usage of approximate entropy finds common application in machine learning algorithms like PCA (Principal Component Analysis). This paper was useful in understanding the behavior of vibrational signals upon fatigue loading, and helped apply the corresponding algorithms in the testing and training stages of the machine learning process.

- (Elangovan et al., 2011) explained using the vibrational signals obtained from the tip of a single point cutting tool during the machining process as a primary feature for the condition monitoring of the tool. The paper also suggests using Principle Component Analysis (PCA) transformed statistical features as an alternative to feature reduction using decision trees. The feature reduction using decision tree and PCA was done separately, and then the results were compared to help identify the best possible option. The experiment made use of the C 4.5 algorithm, and a PCA pre-processor embedded decision tree algorithm. This paper was used to identify the various algorithms that could be used in the project.
- (Karthik Dhayakar et al., 2015) provided a comprehensive discussion about the design and analysis of a motorcycle's front suspension. The paper stated that the main purpose of a motorcycle suspension is to reduce shock impulses that occur while traversing the road. The paper suggested the usage of mono suspensions instead of the conventional telescopic forks. The major faults faced by the telescopic forks were elaborated, namely, leakage and deteriorating quality of fork oil. This helped identify the major problems that are present in a telescopic fork, and the experiment was conducted simulating the aforementioned errors.
- (Marius-Constantin et al., 2009) discussed the methodology used in the testing and simulation of a motor vehicle suspension. The results of a mathematical simulation performed on MATLAB were compared against the data acquired from an experimental set-up to determine the efficiency of the mathematical simulation.

This paper helped understand the procedure to be carried out while performing the experiment on the motorcycle, and also the conditions that are to be monitored.

- (Levy et al., 2005) discussed about the Bicycle suspension's purpose in improving the rider performance and comfort through the isolation of the discomfort that comes as a result of the uneven terrain of the road. The suspension performances of five different vehicles were compared with that of a rigid fork by taking the acceleration at the bicycle's axle and frame. It was reported that acceleration was apparent at two distinct frequency regions, and these regions interacted with different regions in different ways. Air-oil dampers were observed to be the most effective of dampers to isolate the vibration in the vehicle. The paper consisted of a detailed procedure of how to carry out our experiment, and this experiment aided in formulating a corresponding procedure for the project on the motorcycle suspension. The thorough explanation of the working of a telescopic suspension helped to further the understanding of the type of forks, and how to carry out the experiment and obtain results.
- (Dileep et al., 2008) focused on the vibration based maintenance of rotating parts in a Forced Draft fan that is found in common application in boilers. To increase the boiler efficiency, a FD fan forces ambient air into the boiler after sending it through a pre-heater. The fan was observed to suffer from vibrations beyond the safe limit, and it was noted that the fan driving end bearing failed as a result. The bearing was replaced with another one designed to be maintained at the safe limits. The paper explained in detail about the essential details of condition monitoring and its application in an industrial environment. The methods to capture and interpret the vibration signals were also clearly elaborated.
- (Tribology-abc.com, 2016) gave details about viscosity of oils used for damping. It provided data about viscosity of oils at certain temperatures, and their corresponding grades. There are different oil standards available in the market, and this source gave a comparison between these standards, thus providing a conclusive picture about oil viscosity and their grades.

OBJECTIVE AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 OBJECTIVE

To perform condition monitoring of a motorcycle front suspension, and seek to identify two frequently occurring faults, namely change in viscosity of oil, and leakage of oil, and compare them with a good suspension by analyzing their vibration signals obtained for on-road condition. The project ultimately seeks to find the best classifier algorithm from a set of different families of algorithms available, for two different speeds of the vehicle.

3.2 METHODOLOGY

3.2.1 Introduction

The vibration signals were chosen as the parameter to perform the condition monitoring because it is a direct implication of the performance of the suspension. Thus, vibration of the piston of the telescopic fork along the axis of the suspension was decided as the parameter to be observed for this.

3.2.2 Choice of vehicle

There are different types of motorcycles available in the market, such as sports bikes, off-road bikes, and normal passenger bikes. This project concentrates on the passenger bikes due to their abundance in Indian roads. TVS Victor GL 2003 model was selected for this, based on its similarity in design with other passenger bikes, and also its ready availability for our project. Specifications of this vehicle are as follows:

- Engine: Single cylinder 4 stroke, air cooled, 109 cc petrol engine
- Wheels and tires : 2.75*18 –Front and 3*18 -Rear
- Suspension : Telescopic fork, oil damped, 100mm

Hydraulic with co-axial spring

- Kerb weight : 113 kg

3.2.3 Selection of test track

The track plays a major role on the outcome of the experiment. It should replicate a common road in India, and at the same time it should give continuous signals for the purpose of convenient processing of the signals. There are different kinds of roads available such as smooth roads, rough roads, off-road terrain. The performed condition monitoring should be applicable to all these kinds of roads. An improperly laid road with minor rubbles was chosen as the test track for the experiment.

Due to the variety of roads in India, it is not economically feasible to conduct the experiment on all these kinds of roads. For this purpose, construction of an experimental set-up that could simulate different kinds of roads was thought of as an extension to this project. The experimental rig is discussed in detail in chapter 9.

3.2.4 Analysis of data

From the experiment, raw data, i.e., displacement –time plot, and the statistical features of the vibration signals were obtained using a 3-axes accelerometer and a DAQ (Data Acquisition) set-up. The data were then processed using machine learning algorithms in order to find the best classification algorithm for the project. WEKA, an open source machine learning software, contains a comprehensive set of machine learning algorithms of different kinds. The algorithms are programmed in the software, and are aided by an easily understandable GUI (Graphic User Interface) for easy use. Two algorithms each were selected from three different algorithm families, and each of these algorithms was trained to the maximum extent possible.

3.2.5 Conclusion

Thus, the experimental conditions were decided with the TVS Victor–GL as the test vehicle, and the data obtained were then processed in WEKA.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

4.1 Objective

To test the performance of various faulty front suspension forks, and compare them with a good suspension fork in a motorcycle for an on-road condition.

4.2 Apparatus used

- Vehicle :TVS Victor-GL (2003 Model)
- National Instruments 3-Axes Accelerometer-sensor
- Data Acquisition system
- Software used to record the signals: LABVIEW
- UPS to power the DAQ system
- Laptop, to record the acquired signals

4.3 Procedure

- The UPS, Accelerometer, DAQ setup, and the laptop were connected.
- The accelerometer was rigidly attached to the top of the piston in the front suspension fork using adhesive mounting technique as shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2 Mounting of accelerometer

- Once the connections were made, the LABVIEW software was then opened, and the required signal acquisition parameters were set with sampling frequency of 51000 and sampling length as 51000.
- The block diagram connection required to acquire the data was then modeled in LABVIEW to obtain both raw data and statistical features, as shown in figure 3.

Fig. 3 Model diagram connection

- Experimental conditions were maintained as follows:
 - Vehicle: TVS Victor GL
 - Vehicle speed: 15 kmph and 30 kmph
 - Total no of runs in each condition: 5 at 15kmph and 3 at 30kmph speed

- Time of each run: 60 seconds (approx.)
 - Time run for single condition: 300sec (approx.) in 15 kmph and 180 sec in 30 kmph.
 - Number of signals per second: 51000
-
- The experiment was performed with a rider and a pillion, with a total mass of around 150kg including all the experimental apparatus.
 - From the performed experiment, the raw data, i.e., displacement-time graph, and the statistical features were obtained.
 - The experiment was performed for different conditions of the front suspension, namely good suspension, oil leaking suspension, and an oil worn suspension. The fault simulations are discussed in section 4.4.
 - These signals were then organized, and later analyzed using WEKA 3.6.

The overall experimental set-up is shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4 Overall experimental setup

4.4 Fault simulation

As mentioned before, the following conditions were considered for our project:

1. Good suspension – characterized by new fork oil and properly sealed fork.
2. Old suspension with oil whose viscosity has changed.
3. Oil leaking suspension- because of improper sealant.

Even though all these conditions are difficult to be identified in running condition, for the conditions where the suspension system was removed from the motorcycle and analyzed, the first and third conditions are easily characterized, but the second condition needs a quantifiable parameter to characterize. Viscosity is an important property in damping, and is directly affected when the oil is worn out. Hence, the viscosity of the oil which was used for a long time was measured at room temperature, and was characterized as worn out oil, while the new oil was used for the case of good suspension. The new oil was graded SAE10W, equivalent to viscosity of 0.16 stokes at 40°C. Hence, it was decided that the viscosity of oil was to be taken at the same temperature in order to have an accurate comparison.

4.5 Measurement of viscosity

- Objective: To measure the viscosity of an old fork oil at 40 °C using Redwood Viscometer type 1.
- Apparatus Used: Redwood Viscometer (type 1), Thermometer, Soft water, Petrol, 50ml flask, beaker.
- Procedure: First, the viscometer (fig. 5) was thoroughly cleaned with petrol, and the waste was collected in a beaker.

Fig. 5 Redwood viscometer

- The viscometer was made to stand on the viscometer stand.
- Then the viscometer was filled with soft water in the portion outside the test tank up to the indicated level.
- Then the jet was sealed with the ball valve, and the fork oil was poured into the oil cup up to the level of the pointer indicator.
- The water and oil were heated till the temperature of water reached 42 °C. Then the heater was turned off.
- The oil tank was stirred rigorously till both water and oil attained equilibrium at 40 °C.
- Then the ball valve was lifted, and the oil flowing out from the jet at the bottom was collected in a 50ml flask.
- The time taken to collect 50ml of oil was noted down.
- The kinematic viscosity of the oil was then calculated using the measured time, as shown below.

- Calculation :

Time taken to collect 50 ml of oil (t) = 195 seconds

For Redwood viscometer 1,

The Kinematic viscosity (γ) = $0.002 * t - 1.8/t$ in Stokes

$$= 0.002 * 195 - 1.8 / 195 = 0.3808 \text{ stokes}$$

- Result: The viscosity of the old oil was determined to be $\gamma = 0.3808$ stokes at 40°C, while the viscosity of the new oil, which was graded SAE 10W, was 0.16 stokes at 40 °C.

4.6 Conclusion

Thus, the experiment was performed for different fault conditions of front suspensions, with proper characterization, and the vibration signals were obtained. The data were sorted out based on their types. The collected data were then processed using WEKA, as discussed in the next section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Pre-processing

The vibration data, which includes both the raw data and statistical features obtained for each second, is known as a signal. Raw data gives the displacement-time plot while statistical features give more meaningful data. Thus the statistical signals were the required signals. There were around 200 signals obtained for the speed of 15 kmph, and 120 signals were obtained for 30 kmph for each condition of the suspension. From the 200 signals, 20 signals were trimmed off symmetrically to account for experimental errors, and the remaining 180 signals were split into 130 signals as training set, and 50 signals as test set. For the case of 30 kmph speed, 75 signals were set as training set, and 25 signals were set as test set, after removing 20 signals symmetrically to account for experimental errors. Totally 390 signals were set as train set, and 150 as test set, for 15kmph speed, and 225 signals as train set and 75 signals as test set, for 30kmph speed. Once the signals were split, signals of different conditions were sorted along with their labelled conditions in a single file. The order in which the signals were ordered was kept the same for both training and test sets. This process was carried out in Microsoft Excel, and was saved according to the format which was needed by WEKA (.csv).

5.2 Analysis of the data

There were seven statistical features obtained from the experiment. They are as follows:

- Standard Deviation: It is defined as the root mean square deviation of signal values from the arithmetic mean.

$$\text{Standard deviation}(\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}. \quad (3)$$

- **Kurtosis:** Kurtosis indicates the flatness or spike in a vibration signal. Its value is high for the faulty ones.

$$\text{Kurtosis} = \left\{ \frac{n(n+1)}{(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i - \bar{x}}{s} \right)^4 \right\} - \frac{3(n-1)^2}{(n-2)(n-3)}, \quad (4)$$

- **Variance:** It is the square of standard deviation and represents the variance of signal points.

$$\text{Variance} = \sigma^2 \quad (5)$$

- **Skewness:** It is the degree of asymmetry in the distribution of data with its mean.

$$\text{Skewness} = \frac{n}{(n-1)(n-2)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i - \bar{x}}{s} \right)^3. \quad (6)$$

- **Median:** Median is the midpoint of set of data which are ordered in their ascending value.
- **Mode:** Mode is the value that occurs most frequently in a set of data.
- **Summation:** It is the sum of all values in a set of data.

There was one another feature that was recorded incidentally, which was the displacement of the suspension along the axis parallel to the axis of the wheels, whose value was 0 for all the cases. This value was redundant throughout.

Once the data were categorized, sorted out, and the training and test sets were prepared, the next step was to find the most effective classifier algorithm. As mentioned in section 3.2, the two best algorithms each from Tree based, Instance based, and Functions based algorithms were chosen for the study. The theory behind these algorithms were dealt in brief in section 1.4.

5.2.1 Tree based algorithms

- **C4.5 algorithm**

The C4.5 algorithm is dependent on three parameters-minimum number of features required for classification, minimum number of instances required to form a leaf (m), and confidence factor (c). Confidence factor is required for pruning; smaller values incur more pruning.

a. Dimensionality reduction

First, dimensionality reduction, i.e., selecting the optimum number of features required for classification, was done. For that, the training data set for 15kmph speed of the vehicle was fed with all the seven obtained statistical features, keeping the default value of c as 0.25, and m as 2. The decision tree was obtained as shown in figure 6.

The decision tree indicates the importance of each feature in the descending order of their importance, and those features that are not part of the decision tree are considered redundant, and can be discarded. From the decision tree for 15kmph speed, standard deviation-the root feature, kurtosis, and median were chosen as the required statistical feature. Dimensionality reduction was done by first selecting only the root feature to find out the classifier efficiency, and then the root feature along with the next feature in the hierarchy level were selected to find the classification efficiency, and finally, all the three features were selected for classification. The plot of number of features versus classification efficiency was obtained as shown in figure 7.

Fig. 6 Decision tree for J48 with all 8 features, $c = 0.25$, $m = 2$ (15 kmph)

Fig. 7 Training efficiency vs number of features (15 kmph)

The plot showed a peak when minimum number of features is two. Thus, the optimum features required for classification at 15kmph speed are standard deviation and kurtosis.

Similar procedure was performed for vehicle speed of 30 kmph, and the decision tree was obtained, which yielded standard deviation, kurtosis, and skewness as the essential features, as shown in figure 8.

Fig. 8 Decision tree for J48 with all 8 features, $c = 0.25$, $m = 2$ (30 kmph)

Dimensionality reduction was done, for which results are shown in fig.9. The graph reaches the peak for minimum number of features is three, and then the classification efficiency remains at the highest value for further increase in the number of features. However, more the number of features, longer is the time taken for the algorithm to perform the classification, owing to the increase in number of values to be accounted for. Thus, the optimum number of features was fixed as three.

Fig. 9 Training efficiency vs No. of features (30kmph)

b. Optimization of parameters

Once the minimum number of features required was selected, the next parameter that C4.5 depends on is minimum number of instances per leaf (m). It was varied progressively from 0 to 10 in steps of one, and from 10 to 25 in steps of five. The classification efficiencies were obtained for each of these values, for both the speeds. The plot of minimum number of objects per leaf versus efficiency is shown in figures 10 and 11. Actual relation between minimum number of instances and classification accuracy is very complex, and it is best understood when the effect is studied statistically.

Fig. 10 Minimum number of instances (m) vs Training efficiency (15 kmph)

Fig. 11 Minimum number of instances (m) vs Training efficiency (30 kmph)

From the above plots, it was seen that for 15kmph speed, the graph reached its peak when m is 2. Hence, we can say that $m=2$ is the optimum value for classification at 15kmph speed.

For the 30kmph speed, it was seen that classification efficiency is highest for values of $m=1$ and $m=2$. Since lesser the number of objects, lower is the processing time for the classifier, $m=1$ was set as the optimum value for 30kmph speed.

After the optimum minimum number of instances was chosen, optimum value of confidence factor (c) had to be found out. It can take values from zero to one. To study the variation of classification accuracy with confidence factor, the confidence factor was varied from 0 to 1 in steps of 0.1. The plot is as shown in figures 12 and 13, for both the speeds.

Fig. 12 Confidence factor vs Training efficiency (15kmph)

Fig.13 Confidence factor vs Training efficiency (30kmph)

From the plot of confidence factor versus efficiency for the speed of 15kmph, it was seen that the training efficiency reached the highest value when $c = 0.6$, and remained the same for further increase in c . However, $c = 0.2$ was chosen as the optimum value because the difference in classification efficiency from that at $c = 0.6$ is negligible, and at the same time smaller value of c creates a more robust classifier, owing to greater pruning.

In the case of 30 kmph speed, the training efficiency reaches the highest value at $c=0.2$, and remains at peak for further increase in c . Thus, $c = 0.2$ was chosen as the optimum value. This concludes the designing of J48, an implementation of C4.5 algorithm, for both the speeds.

- **NBTree algorithm**

- a. Dimensionality reduction

Next, the NB Tree algorithm was chosen for classification. The decision tree for this algorithm was obtained as shown in figure 14 for a speed of 15 kmph.

Tree View

Fig. 14 Decision tree for NB Tree (15kmph)

From the decision tree, it was seen that kurtosis, summation, mode and skewness were the required statistical features for classification.

Then the same steps as done for the case of C4.5 algorithm were repeated, comparing the classification efficiency for different number of features chosen hierarchically. The plot of number of features versus classification efficiency is shown in figure 15.

Fig. 15 No. of features vs Training efficiency (15 kmph)

This plot showed that the training efficiency progressively increased with increase in number of features, and reached the highest value when number of features was 8. This indicated that all the features were required for efficient classification. Similar steps were followed for 30kmph speed, and the decision tree was obtained as shown in figure 16.

Fig. 16 Decision tree for NBTree (30kmph)

Fig. 17 Number of features vs Classification efficiency –NB Tree (15kmph)

The plot of training efficiency versus number of features for both 30 kmph and 20 kmph speeds showed a unique trend compared to the previous plots. Usually, the number of objects that appear in the decision tree is always less than the total number of features obtained, and moreover, the training efficiency when all the features were selected was less than the training efficiency for optimum number of features chosen by performing the dimensionality reduction. In these cases, however, the training efficiency was higher when all eight features were selected in comparison to the training efficiency when only those features that appeared in the decision tree were selected. Thus, in this case, optimum number of features is selected as 8.

The NB Tree algorithm was not dependent on any other parameter, and so the design of the algorithm was complete with this stage.

After the classifiers were designed, they were validated with the help of the test sets. For C4.5 algorithm and NB Tree algorithm, the test data sets were fed in, and the analysis was performed with the optimum values of their dependent parameters. The test results are shown in table 1.

Table 1 Test efficiencies for NB tree and J48

Algorithm	Bike Speed (kmph)	Test efficiency (%)
NBTree	15	95.5695
	30	75.9259
J48	15	96.3185
	30	81.4815

The classifications and misclassifications of data are represented with the help of confusion matrix. The confusion matrix of each of the algorithms at two different speeds are as shown in Tables 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Table 2 Confusion matrix for test run –C4.5 (15 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
69	6	0	A- Good
0	24	0	B - Oil Leak
1	0	58	C - Old oil

Table 3 Confusion matrix for test run –C4.5 (30 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
11	7	0	A- Good
3	15	0	B - Oil Leak
0	0	18	C - Old oil

Table 4 Confusion matrix for test run –NB Tree (15 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
70	5	0	A- Good
0	24	0	B - Oil Leak
2	0	57	C - Old oil

Table 5 Confusion matrix for test run –NB Tree (30 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
70	5	0	A- Good
0	24	0	B - Oil Leak
2	0	57	C - Old oil

The interpretation of confusion matrices is presented here. The first row represents the good suspension. The first element in the first row (1, 1) depicts the number of signals that represented good suspension, and were actually been classified as good suspension. The second element in the first row (1, 2) represents the number of good suspension data that were classified as leaking suspension. The third row represents the number of good suspension data that were classified as old suspension. Similarly, the second row represents the leaked suspension, and the third row represents the old suspension. Thus, the diagonal elements in the confusion matrix represent the data that have been classified correctly, and the non-diagonal elements are the wrongly classified data.

From the classification accuracy information in Table 1, and from the confusion matrices, it was seen that C4.5 algorithm offered better results than NB Tree algorithm in test set even though both of them offered the same results in training set. Also, it was seen that classification is more accurate at 15 kmph than at 30 kmph. The reason that can best explain this deviation is that the overall vibration of the vehicle increases with the increase in vehicle speed, and this interferes with the signals obtained for the suspension vibration from road disturbances.

5.2.2 Instance based algorithms (IB1 and K*)

IB1 Algorithm was not dependent on any parameter, thus this algorithm did not require any optimization. The train sets were fed directly, and the corresponding training efficiencies were obtained. Once the algorithm was trained, its validity was checked with the help of test sets, and the test efficiencies were obtained. This process was performed for data acquired for both 30 kmph and 15 kmph vehicle speeds.

K* Algorithm was dependent on one parameter known as Global blending parameter (b), which specifies number of instances in the algorithm. The parameter can take values from 0-100. Thus in the training of the k* algorithm, the global blend parameter was varied from 0-100 in steps of 10, and in each case the training efficiency was obtained as 100%. Thus. the optimum value of global blending parameter could not be studied with training. So, it was decided that the optimum blending parameter should be found out by studying the variation of test-classification efficiency. So, the algorithm was run for values of b varying from 0 to 100 in steps of 10, and for each case the test

classification efficiency was obtained. The plot of test classification efficiency versus global blending parameter was plotted as shown in figure18. The details of this algorithm and the parameter are beyond the scope of this project, and are not discussed in detail.

Fig. 18 Classification efficiency vs Global Blend B -k* (15kmph)

The above plot reached its peak at two points, namely at $b=10$ and $b=40$. For faster processing of the algorithm, $b=10$ was chosen as the optimum value of global blend parameter. Similarly for 30 kmph speed, the variation of test-classification efficiency with the global blend parameter was plotted as shown in figure 19.

Fig. 19 Classification efficiency vs Global Blend B -k* (30kmph)

From this graph, it was seen that the test classification efficiency was the highest for $b=70$ and $b=80$. Considering the same reason as in the previous case, the smaller value, that is, $b=70$, was chosen as the optimum value for 30 kmph speed.

The results obtained from both the algorithms are shown in table 6, and their confusion matrices are as shown in tables 7, 8, 9, and 10.

Table 6 Test efficiencies for Lazy algorithms

Algorithm	Bike Speed (kmph)	Test efficiency (%)
IB1	15	94.9367
	30	71.6296
Kstar	15	92.4051
	30	87.037

Table 7 Confusion matrix for test run –IB1 (15 kmph)

A	B	C	← Classified as
68	6	1	A- Good
0	24	0	B - Oil Leak
1	0	58	C - Old oil

Table 8 Confusion matrix for test run –IB1 (30 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
12	6	0	A- Good
5	13	0	B - Oil Leak
0	0	18	C - Old oil

Table 9 Confusion matrix for test run –K* (15 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
69	5	1	A- Good
5	18	1	B - Oil Leak
0	0	59	C - Old oil

Table 10 Confusion matrix for test run –K* (30 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
15	3	0	A- Good
4	14	0	B - Oil Leak
0	0	18	C - Old oil

5.2.3 Functions based algorithms

Logistic Regression was dependent on two parameters, namely ridge factor (R) and number of iterations (M). These two values are automatically fixed based on the input given to the algorithm, and thus do not require any optimization. So, the algorithm was directly trained using the train set signals, and the results were obtained. It was then validated using the test set, and the corresponding test results were recorded.

Sequential Minimal Optimization, an implementation of Support Vector Machine in WEKA did not depend on any parameter. Thus no optimization was required. The algorithm was trained initially with the train set, and was later validated with the test set.

The results obtained from both these algorithms are summarized in table 11, and the corresponding confusion matrices are shown in tables 12, 13, 14, and 15.

Table 11 Test efficiencies for function based algorithms

Algorithm	Bike Speed (kmph)	Test efficiency (%)
SMO	15	94.9367
	30	74.0741
Logistic	15	90.5063
	30	77.7778

Table 12 Confusion matrix for test run –LR (15 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
61	7	7	A- Good
1	23	0	B - Oil Leak
0	0	59	C - Old oil

Table 13 Confusion matrix for test run –LR (30 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
13	5	0	A- Good
5	11	2	B - Oil Leak
0	0	18	C - Old oil

Table 14 Confusion matrix for test run –SMO (15 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
70	5	0	A- Good
2	22	0	B - Oil Leak
1	0	58	C - Old oil

Table 15 Confusion matrix for test run –SMO (30 kmph)

A	B	C	←Classified as
10	8	0	A- Good
6	12	0	B - Oil Leak
0	0	18	C - Old oil

CONCLUSION

6.0 CONCLUSION

The results obtained from all the six algorithms are summarized in tables 16 and 17 for vehicle speeds of 15 kmph and 30 kmph respectively.

Table 16 Summary of results for 15 kmph speed

Algorithm	Data set	Classification accuracy (%)
DT – J48 All 8 statistical features $c = 0.25$, $m = 2$	Train Set	98.9873
	Test Set	96.2025
DT – J48 Only Standard deviation and kurtosis $c=0.2$, $m=2$	Train Set	99.2405
	Test Set	96.3185
DT-NBTree with all 8 features	Train Set	99.2405
	Test Set	95.5696
Lazy- IB1 with all 8 features	Train Set	100
	Test Set	94.9367
Lazy- K-star with all 8 features $B= 10$, $M= a$	Train Set	100
	Test Set	92.4051
Function- Logistic $R= 1.0E-8$, $M=-1$	Train Set	97.9747
	Test Set	90.5063
Function- SMO (Weka implementation of SVM)	Train Set	96.2025
	Test Set	94.9367

Table 17 Summary of results for 30 kmph speed

Algorithm	Data set	Classification accuracy (%)
DT – J48 All 8 statistical features $c = 0.25, m = 2$	Train Set	88.3408
	Test Set	81.4815
DT – J48 S.D, kurtosis, and skewness $c = 0.2, m = 1$	Train Set	88.3408
	Test Set	81.4815
DT-NBTree with all 8 features	Train Set	89.2377
	Test Set	75.9259
Lazy- IB1 with all 8 features	Train Set	100
	Test Set	79.6296
Lazy- K-star with all 8 features $B= 70, M= a$	Train Set	100
	Test Set	87.0737
Function- Logistic $R= 1.0E-8, M=-1$	Train Set	83.4081
	Test Set	77.7778
Function- SMO (Weka implementation of SVM)	Train Set	77.5785
	Test Set	74.0741

Out of all the algorithms considered, C4.5 algorithm exhibited maximum test efficiency for 15kmph speed, and the K-star algorithm exhibited maximum test efficiency for 30kmph speed.

From all the results obtained, it was seen that the testing classification efficiency was invariably lower than the training efficiency. This is due to the in-built errors in the classifier algorithm as well as the errors involved in classification.

Moreover, it was also observed that classification is more accurate at 15kmph than at 30kmph. The reason that can best explain this deviation is that the overall vibration of the vehicle increases with the increase in speed of the vehicle, and this interferes with the signals obtained for the suspension vibration from road disturbances.

FUTURE WORK

In recent times, performance of different parts of automobiles are sensed, and any fault is reported to the rider with the help of LED indicators. One such example is the tyre pressure indicator to caution the driver about any shortage of air in the tyre. There have been indicators for fuel level for a long time now. In the future, after a thorough study of the suspensions of motorcycles, manufacturers could append an indicator in the dashboard of the motorcycle, through a programmable chip that could indicate the condition of the suspension, and alert the driver in case of any faults. This way the rider would know precisely the fault in the suspension, and when to fix them. This would confirm a safe ride, supported by a less expensive and effective maintenance.

As discussed in section 3.2, an experimental set-up that could simulate different road conditions was thought of as an extension to the project. For this purpose, a prototype of an experimental set-up that could simulate a bumpy road was built and tested. This set-up, however, did not give satisfying results as it required a motor with better power than what was used, and certain other modifications in the design. Because of the financial and time constraints, this experimental set-up was not continued further. Perhaps this could be worked upon in the future to have a universal road simulator for suspension testing. The details of this work are described in Appendix I.

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APPENDIX I

EXPERIMENTAL RIG**1. Objective of the rig**

A rig was to be constructed which will provide periodic vibrations of equal amplitude in order to check the performance of the suspension system. This was conceptualized to simulate the vibrations in various road conditions, with varying degrees of bumps, rubble, pebbles, rocks etc. By changing the profile of cam, different throw could be achieved, and thus different road conditions could be simulated. Our first attempt was to replicate a bumpy road condition.

2. Construction**2.1 Construction of cam**

A cam was manufactured from soft wood. The dimensions of the cam are as shown in Figure 20.

Fig. 20 Cam dimensions

A block of wood was sourced, and operations such as shaping, planning, and wood cutting were carried out. A hole of 20 mm diameter was also drilled for the cam to rest on a shaft for the purpose of rotation. A throw of 45 mm was decided, based on the average size of a bump on a bumpy road, obtained from a sample collected from a bumpy road.

2.2 Construction of the base

For the purpose of supporting the entire system of the rig, hollow rectangular pipes were sourced. The dimensions of the pipe were 70*30 mm, with a thickness of 1 mm.

These pipes were cut, ground and welded according to the design, and suitable holes were drilled to provide appropriate mounting points for the components of the transmission.

2.3 Motor

A motor of rating 0.5 HP, 1440 rpm, 3 phase, 5 mm key slot was chosen to act as the drive for the rig. Calculations were done to estimate the required torque and speed of the cam to achieve the required throw, and it was found that the maximum speed of rotation of the cam should be 72 rpm.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total weight} &= \text{vehicle weight} + \text{rider} \\ &= 113 + 80 = 193\text{kg}\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Load on front wheels} = 193/2 = 96.5\text{kg} = 965\text{N}$$

$P = n * m * g * h / t$, where

m=mass to be lifted

h= throw of the vehicle

g=acceleration due to gravity

t=time to attain the throw

n=factor of safety=2

By knowing the mass, throw, and based on the available motor, the time required was calculated. Through this the required speed reduction was calculated to be 1:20.

2.4 Gearbox

A worm gear box of reduction ratio 1:20, with driving shaft diameter 10 mm, and key slot 5mm, and driven shaft diameter 22 mm, and key slot 6 mm, was used to provide the required speed reduction. The axes of transmission are perpendicular.

2.5 Shaft

A solid shaft made of mild steel, having a diameter of 20 mm, was used to support the cam, after the reduction in speed at the gearbox. The shaft was provided with key slots of 6 mm for the purpose of coupling with the gearbox, and to mount the flange and bolt coupling of the cam.

2.6 Couplings

Flange couplings were used to couple the output shaft of the motor and the driving shaft of the gearbox, and to couple the driven shaft of the gearbox and the shaft supporting the cam. A flange and bolt type coupling was used to hold the cam in place on the shaft by mounting them on either side. Six holes (three on each side) of diameter 5mm were drilled to insert screws into the wooden material of the cam. The screws coupled the cam to the flange, which in turn was coupled to the shaft. Three pairs of flanges were used, and they were bored to the required dimensions.

2.7 Keys

For coupling the flanges to the shafts, square key rods were used. They had specifications of 5x5 mm and 6x6 mm, and they were cut and ground to suit the suitable length.

2.8 Bearing

A plumber block bearing of internal diameter 20 mm was used to support the farther end of the cam shaft.

2.9 Fasteners

Fasteners were utilized as required to hold all the components perfectly rigid with respect to the base on which they were mounted.

2.10 Arresting the base

A suitable location having desired soil properties was chosen to fix the base of the rig into the ground. This was done to minimize the possibility of vibrations arising from the motor and gearbox interfering with the vibrations detected by the accelerometer on the suspensions.

2.11 Support for the front wheel

A wide rectangular hollow pipe was welded parallel to the cam shaft to provide support to the front tyre, so that the load on the cam would be minimized.

3. Results

Upon running the experiment, there were dips in the speed of rotation of the cam whenever it came in contact with the bottom most point of the tire. Despite providing a support that would offer a reaction force in the vertical direction, and a manual exertion on the handle bars of the bike, the torque was not sufficient enough for the cam to have any noticeable effect on the suspension travel. Observations were recorded. The lone effect that the cam had on the bike was throwing the wheel in the vertical direction, and not the suspensions.

For the suspension to function properly, a strong force is required to be imposed on the handle bars or the upper mounting points of the suspension. But doing so only resulted in the cam not having enough torque, hence coming to a stop.

The overall set-up is shown in figure 21.

Fig. 21 Experimental rig

4. Possible solutions

Using a more powerful motor of about 2 HP rating may provide sufficient torque to achieve the required compression and elongation of the suspension forks. Better designing of the rig to minimize losses in power transmission at the couplings can also be arrived at after further scrutiny. (R, 1996)